

Under review

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

Deliverable D5.3 - Report on generated media literacy material and citizen engagement

WP5 – Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

Version 2.0 | 29 August 2025

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

Document History

Deliverable Title	Report on generated media literacy material and citizen engagement
Brief Description	The report will provide a comprehensive analysis of the materials selected or created to raise awareness and increase the resilience of citizens against climate change disinformation. These materials will include short videos, articles, guides, and practical tips, all aimed at enhancing media literacy and critical-thinking skills. By doing so, they will strengthen citizens' ability to recognize and counter misleading claims and distinguish facts from disinformation. The report will also highlight the synergies between Task 5.3 and other related tasks, such as Task 5.1, Task 3.3, Task 3.5, and Task 2.2.
WP number	5
Lead Beneficiary	ATC
Author(s)	Spyridoula Markou, Adam Doulgerakis
Deliverable Due Date	31/08/2025
Actual Delivery Date	29/08/2025
Nature of the Deliverable	R - Report
Dissemination Level	PU - Public

Date	Ver.	Contributors	Comment
08/10/2024	0.1	Spyridoula Markou, Adam Doulgerakis	Draft structure of the deliverable
29/05/2025	0.2	Spyridoula Markou	Selected and produced material / Modules
16/06/2025	0.3	Spyridoula Markou	Articles
19/06/2025	0.4	Spyridoula Markou	Videos / Graphics
27/06/2025	0.5	Spyridoula Markou	Resources
08/07/2025	0.6	Spyridoula Markou	Resources / Modules Introduction / Synergies
15/07/2025	0.7	Spyridoula Markou	Screenshots of website and material

21/07/2025	0.8	Spyridoula Markou, Adam Doulgerakis	Final initial draft ready for internal review
31/07/2025	1.0	Lucía Morano, Judith Bielsa	Internal Reviewer's comments and feedback
07/08/2025	1.1	Marina Mattera, Alfredo Reder	PM's and WP5 Leader comments and feedback
29/08/2025	2.0	Spyridoula Markou, Adam Doulgerakis	Integration of internal reviewer's comments and final version

Table of Contents

Document History	2
1. Executive Summary	6
2. Introduction	6
2.1 Media Literacy.....	7
2.2 Disinformation and misinformation.....	8
2.3 Strengthen citizen resilience against climate change disinformation	10
2.4 Structure of the deliverable	11
3. Selected and produced material.....	12
3.1 Selected material	13
3.2 Produced material.....	15
3.2.1 Modules.....	16
3.2.2 Articles.....	24
3.2.3 Graphics.....	27
3.2.4 Videos.....	33
4. Synergies between Task 5.3 and other tasks	35
5. Conclusion.....	38
References	40
Appendix	42
List of resources collected.....	42

Table of Figures

Image 1: The External Material subpage.	14
Image 2: The modules are organised under two main sections of the Academy website.....	16
Image 3: The Introduction to Media Literacy module.	17
Image 4: the Digital Literacy module.	18

Image 5: The Critical Thinking / Fallacies module.....18

Image 6: The Evaluating Information Sources module.....19

Image 7: The Fact-Checking and Verification module.20

Image 8: The Engaging in Online Discussions / Online Safety module.20

Image 9: The Psychology of Belief and Disinformation module.21

Image 10: The Understanding Climate Change module.22

Image 11: The Climate Change Communication module.22

Image 12: The Climate Change Disinformation Tactics module.23

Image 13: The Climate Change Disinformation Narratives module.23

Image 14: The Disinformation Campaigns - Case Studies module.24

Image 15: The blog section of the DA website.25

Image 16: Graphic - The five techniques of science denial by John Cook.27

Image 17: Graphic - Filter bubbles and echo chambers.28

Image 18: Graphic - Boolean search techniques.29

Image 19: Graphic – Digital Literate Person.30

Image 20: Graphic - Fake Accounts.....30

Image 21: Graphic - What is an argument? A quick guide to logic and reasoning.31

Image 22: Graphic - Think before you share – Media literacy tips for navigating climate information.32

Image 23: Screenshot from the video “Introducing the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation”.....33

Image 24: Screenshot from the video “Principles for ethical content creation”.34

Image 25: Screenshot from the video “The 5 Ws”.35

Image 26: The categories of the AGORA quiz.....37

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the work carried out under Task 5.3 of the Adaptation AGORA project, focusing on the creation and selection of media literacy materials designed to help citizens build resilience against climate change disinformation. The aim was to make media literacy and critical thinking more accessible — not just in theory, but in practice — so that people are better equipped to spot misleading claims and engage meaningfully with climate issues.

Throughout the task, we selected and developed a range of educational materials, including interactive modules, videos, infographics, and articles. We also researched and reviewed existing resources from trusted organisations and experts in the field and selected over 100 among them to be included in the project's results. The material was produced with the purpose of being practical, user-friendly, and relevant to everyday digital life. These materials are now available through the project's main platforms, notably the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation and the Agora Community Hub.

The report also outlines how these outputs interface with other components of the project. For example, we used the content created under Task 5.3 to develop the quiz questions, which feed into the gamified mobile app in Task 2.2. At the same time, articles and blog posts contribute directly to community engagement via the Agora Hub (Task 3.3). The content also aligns with citizen science efforts from Task 5.1 and is fully integrated into the Academy under Task 3.5.

Rather than a stand-alone effort, the material created under Task 5.3 is part of a broader approach to strengthen public trust, raise awareness, and support active participation in climate adaptation. The materials are intended for individuals, educators, civil society actors, and anyone who wants to make sense of the online information landscape and take part in tackling disinformation. Although the challenge of climate-related disinformation is unlikely to diminish in the near future, we hope that these resources will enable individuals to feel more confident, better informed, and empowered to take meaningful action within their communities.

2. Introduction

Climate change is no longer a remote or hypothetical threat; it is already manifesting and having tangible impacts on communities across Europe and around the globe. From devastating wildfires in Greece and catastrophic floods in Germany to prolonged droughts in southern Spain, the warning

signs are everywhere (Directorate-General for Climate Action, 2022). While scientists continue to sound the alarm, it is also true that we still have time to act and reduce the most severe impacts, provided that timely and decisive action is taken (IPCC, 2018). That is where communication and education come in.

Talking about climate change isn't always easy. People are occupied, sceptical, or simply unsure about what they can do. At the same time, misinformation and disinformation are spreading rapidly online and making the public conversation even more confusing. To make things worse, social media algorithms often boost false or emotionally charged content, making it harder to find reliable information (Milli et al., 2025; Flore et al., 2019).

This chapter explores how media literacy, awareness about false information, and strategies to build resilience can help individuals and communities respond more confidently to climate change disinformation. By providing citizens with the tools to recognise misleading content, critically assess online information, and engage in informed action, we can help safeguard public trust and foster more effective responses to climate change (Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy, 2024).

This is also the goal of the Adaptation AGORA project, which works to strengthen people's skills and knowledge through accessible, digital learning tools. The project includes two dedicated platforms: the [Digital Academy against Climate Disinformation](#), which helps citizens identify and understand climate-related falsehoods, and the [Digital Academy to Access and Use Climate Data and Monitor Climate Risks](#), which supports users in making sense of climate data and local adaptation needs. These skills are further enhanced through the [Agora Community Hub](#) and the [mobile app](#). As part of Task 5.3, the consortium partners have selected and created educational material that will be made available across different Adaptation AGORA digital outputs, aiming to raise awareness, improve media literacy, and ultimately increase societal resilience to climate threats and disinformation.

2.1 Media Literacy

Media literacy isn't just about knowing how to use a computer or browse the internet. It is about understanding how media messages are created, why they're made the way they are, and how they can shape how we see the world and influence our actions. The European Commission defines media literacy as *"the ability to access the media, to understand and to critically evaluate different aspects of the media and media contents and to create communications in a variety of contexts"*. Media messages include informational and creative content, such as texts, sounds, and images, conveyed through different forms of communication – television, cinema, video, websites, radio,

video games, and online communities. The Commission also emphasises the importance of using these messages in a critical, active, and creative manner (European Commission, 2007).

In today's world, where people are constantly scrolling through news feeds and social media platforms, it is more important than ever to be able to distinguish between reliable and manipulated content, especially when it comes to climate change.

Many people believe they're good at spotting fake news, but studies suggest that is not always the case. In fact, false stories often spread faster than real ones, especially if they provoke a strong emotional reaction (Ecker et al, 2022; Lewandowsky et al., 2020) like anger or fear. Algorithms on social platforms are partly to blame. They're designed to keep users engaged, which means they tend to promote content that gets a lot of clicks, and that is often the most sensational or polarising (Flore et al., 2019).

This situation makes it harder for people to access clear, science-based information about climate issues. And that is a problem, because without access to trustworthy sources, citizens can't make informed decisions or hold their leaders to account.

To be truly media literate, people need to:

- Question where a piece of information is coming from. *Is the source credible?*
- Think about who benefits from the message. *Is someone trying to promote a political or commercial agenda?*
- Recognise when content is designed to manipulate emotions, especially if it makes them feel angry, helpless or scared.

Developing these skills doesn't happen overnight. It requires continuous learning, curiosity, and ideally, education systems that make media literacy a core part of what is taught in schools. According to the OECD, education systems can play a big role in helping students understand not just climate science, but also the role of media, power and persuasion in shaping public opinion (Nusche et al., 2024).

Even outside of school, there are ways people can build their skills by listening to podcasts, joining local climate groups, or simply having conversations with friends and family about what they've read or heard online (Directorate-General for Climate Action, 2022). The more we talk about it, the more we learn.

2.2 Disinformation and misinformation

The distinction between misinformation and disinformation can be confusing, as both involve false or misleading content. The distinction lies in the intention behind it. According to the European

Commission, disinformation refers to deliberately false or misleading information that is shared with the aim of deceiving people or advancing political or economic interests, and it can lead to significant public harm. In contrast, misinformation is false or inaccurate information shared without the intent to mislead, even though it can still have harmful consequences (European Commission, 2025).

Climate disinformation is not a new phenomenon, but its reach and sophistication have significantly increased in the digital age. While some forms of disinformation continue to follow traditional narratives — such as denying the existence of climate change or its human causes — many recent examples are more nuanced. Rather than outright denial, they aim to delay climate action or create confusion by shifting blame, undermining confidence in adaptation and mitigation strategies, or claiming that climate policies will negatively affect employment, livelihoods, or personal freedoms (European Commission, 2024).

Disinformation is frequently crafted to provoke strong emotional responses, such as fear, anger, or mistrust. These emotional triggers contribute to the rapid spread of such content, particularly on digital platforms where algorithms prioritise engagement. For instance, mayors in various European cities have been the target of false narratives alleging plans to ban meat or enforce restrictive urban policies. In reality, these initiatives were aimed at promoting sustainability and reducing emissions (Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, 2024). The success of such narratives lies not in their accuracy but in their simplicity, emotional appeal, and repetition.

Misinformation, by contrast, is often shared by individuals who believe the information to be true. This might include sharing a video that falsely claims electric vehicles are more polluting than traditional ones, or reposting content that exaggerates the impact of wind turbines on wildlife. These examples are particularly complicated to address because they often appear plausible and are circulated in good faith.

Addressing both misinformation and disinformation requires a multifaceted approach:

- There is a need for stronger regulation and greater transparency. Online platforms must take greater responsibility in curating content, especially regarding the influence of algorithms and targeted advertising (European Parliament & Council of the EU, 2022).
- Education and media literacy should be prioritised. Citizens should be equipped with the skills needed to critically assess information and recognise manipulative techniques (Lewandowsky et al., 2020).
- Credible and trusted voices must be amplified. Scientists, journalists, and community leaders must engage actively in public discourse, providing accessible and fact-based information while fostering dialogue.

Finally, it is essential to recognise that factual accuracy alone is often insufficient. People are more likely to respond to messages that align with their identity, values, and sense of trust (Kahan, 2013; Berinsky, 2017). For this reason, climate communication should aim to be not only accurate but also relatable and meaningful to different audiences, rather than relying solely on data-driven messaging.

2.3 Strengthen citizen resilience against climate change disinformation

Resilience isn't just about upgrading infrastructure or responding to natural disasters; it is also about equipping citizens to deal with misleading information, confusion, and doubt. When we talk about *citizen resilience* in the context of climate change, we mean giving individuals the skills and necessary information to identify false or misleading content, stay informed, and remain engaged in both mitigation and adaptation efforts (Daume, 2024).

Adaptation — the steps we take to adjust to existing climate impacts — depends heavily on public understanding and action. But when disinformation claims that adaptation is unnecessary, ineffective, or part of some hidden agenda, it can create resistance or delay essential actions (European Commission, 2024). That is why strengthening resilience against climate disinformation is a key part of preparing societies for what is ahead.

So, what does this kind of resilience actually look like? First, it involves promoting critical thinking. Citizens need to be equipped to ask the right questions: *Who is sharing this message? What is their motivation? Does it feel emotionally manipulative?* This doesn't mean people should mistrust everything, just that they should pause, reflect, and look for reliable sources. According to inoculation theory, simply exposing people to common manipulation techniques (like false dilemmas or conspiracy claims) can help build resistance, much like a vaccine strengthens the immune system (van der Linden et al., 2020; Cook, Lewandowsky, & Ecker, 2017).

Second, resilience means improving access to trustworthy information. When reliable climate information is buried under viral hoaxes and clickbait, many people simply won't have the time or energy to search for the facts. Governments, journalists, researchers, and civil society actors all have a role to play in making adaptation information clear, relatable, and easy to find.

Third, it is also about speaking to people's concerns and what matters in their everyday lives. Disinformation spreads because it tells stories that feel familiar or personal. So, countering it takes more than just presenting the facts; it requires connection. Effective climate communication should highlight local benefits (cleaner air, safer homes, stronger communities) and make clear that adaptation is not about giving things up, but about protecting what matters most (Directorate-General for Climate Action, 2022).

And finally, true resilience means addressing the underlying causes that make people vulnerable to disinformation in the first place, things like low trust in institutions, social exclusion, and lack of access to quality education (Flore et al., 2019). Media literacy is only one piece of the puzzle. For change to last, citizens also need to feel empowered, heard, and included.

This is where the Adaptation AGORA project plays an important role. Through the Digital Academy against Climate Disinformation, the project supports citizens in developing the skills they need to recognise and respond to false or misleading climate-related content. As part of Task 5.3, the consortium partners selected and created a wide range of materials — including educational modules, reports, graphics, videos, articles, and curated resources — specifically designed to address existing gaps and respond to real needs identified across different communities, based on the findings from the pilot activities conducted during the project. These materials aim to strengthen public resilience by helping people improve their critical thinking, better understand the tactics used in disinformation, and feel more confident engaging in climate-related discussions and initiatives. The overall goal is not just to share knowledge, but to build the capacity of individuals to actively counter misinformation and take part in local and national efforts to adapt to the climate crisis. This work complements other capacity-building activities within WP5 that tackle disinformation, such as the John Cook workshop held at the beginning of the project, creating a coherent foundation for the project's wider objectives.

Disinformation is likely to remain part of the landscape for years to come. But with the right support, people can become more confident in what they know, more skilled in how they learn, and more resilient in how they respond.

2.4 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is organised into four main chapters, each focusing on a different part of the work carried out under Task 5.3. After the Introduction, which outlines the importance of media literacy and citizen resilience in the face of climate disinformation, the second chapter explores these themes in more depth. It explains what media literacy really means in today's digital world, clarifies the difference between misinformation and disinformation, and discusses practical ways to help individuals and communities build resilience.

The third chapter presents the materials that were either selected or produced as part of the task. It covers everything from educational modules and articles to infographics, videos, and curated external resources. Each type of content is briefly explained, with a focus on how it contributes to improving critical thinking, media awareness, and climate understanding.

The final chapter highlights how Task 5.3 connects with other parts of the project. It explains how the materials created here support the Digital Academy, the gamified mobile app, and the Agora

Community Hub, showing the value of a cross-cutting approach. At the end of the deliverable, readers can also find a list of references and an appendix with the full set of resources gathered during this phase of the project.

3. Selected and produced material

As part of Task 5.3, ATC, together with CMCC, APRE, IIASA and IBE, worked on creating and selecting different types of material that would help strengthen citizens' resilience against climate change disinformation. The aim was not only to raise awareness and help individuals build their own critical thinking and media literacy skills, but also to provide useful resources that could be used as a guide by educators and trainers.

These materials were designed to highlight the most relevant skills needed to recognise and respond to disinformation, such as verifying sources, understanding how media narratives work, and engaging safely and effectively in online discussions. Some of the content was newly produced, while others were selected from existing resources, and all of it was designed to be clear, practical, and useful for a broad audience. The material includes modules, short videos, articles, and graphics that will enhance the citizens' skills and help them think more carefully about what they read and share.

These resources are made available through the [Digital Agora platform](#) (Task 3.3) and are also part of the [Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation](#) described in Task 3.5. In addition, the content is fed into the gamified mobile app that has been developed under Task 2.2. The paragraphs that follow provide more information about the modules and other supporting materials that were created or selected during this period (M18 to M32).

The materials that were selected or created focused on building the skills people need to understand better how media works and how disinformation spreads. These skills were identified not only through existing research but also through insights gathered during the project's pilot activities in [Dresden](#), [Malmö](#), [Zaragoza](#), and [Rome](#). Each pilot brought together citizens and stakeholders to discuss their experiences with climate communication, misinformation, and the challenges they face in accessing and trusting information. These discussions helped shape a set of resources that respond to real needs, reflect different local contexts, and support more inclusive, critical, and informed engagement with the media.

Once these materials were produced, an additional positive deviation took place within the Adaptation AGORA project, which was the participation in the 2025 Global Symposium on Climate

Justice and Impacted Populations held on July 28-31. During the event, policymakers, United Nations project managers and representatives from various regions across the globe took part in one of the largest meetings between experts in climate change justice and inequalities, actively being engaged in workshops and focus group activities. The Adaptation AGORA Disinformation Academy was presented, following a discussion on the lack of awareness certain groups of citizens have and the barriers this presents. Experts agreed that such tools could be beneficial in various regions of the world and could be potentially introduced as elements within the education system to start generating awareness at a young age and combat disinformation trends. Furthermore, it served as a feedback mechanism to expand and improve the content of the academy during the final four months of the project, which constitutes the last iteration process of these elements within the project.

3.1 Selected material

As part of Task 5.3, the partners involved compiled a final set of 106 diverse resources ([Appendix](#)) aimed at strengthening media literacy skills in the context of climate change and disinformation. The selection reflects a broad mix of formats, themes, and target groups. The resources cover essential areas such as critical thinking, evaluating sources, climate change narratives, logical fallacies, digital safety, and more. This number does not include all the resources that were used within the educational modules developed as part of the task.

Among the materials are practical guides, short videos, interactive learning platforms, articles, podcasts, infographics, and training toolkits. Some of them are designed for individual learning, while others are suitable for educators or organisations delivering workshops and training. The collection includes both introductory-level and more advanced content, supporting a wide range of learners, from students and general audiences to professionals and trainers.

The resources were chosen based on their relevance to the modules of the Adaptation AGORA Digital Academy, their educational value, clarity, and accessibility. The selection was also guided by a set of core skills identified as essential for enhancing individuals' capabilities to navigate today's complex media environment. Most of the selected materials are openly available online, and when possible, priority was given to those with clear licensing terms (e.g. Creative Commons). A few resources with no explicit licensing were also included, given their strong alignment with the project's learning goals and practical value.

All 106 resources will be made available on the [Resources](#) section of the Adaptation AGORA website. In addition, a curated set of external materials is featured on the [External Material](#) subpage under the Media Literacy section. This helps users access useful content quickly without having to go through the full list.

This shortlist on the External Material subpage includes resources from a subset of the overall categories, specifically, educational modules, guides, reports, podcasts, and toolboxes/repositories. These resources were selected based on the high quality of the work, their direct relevance to the project’s aims, and their potential to engage and support a broad audience. It is important to clarify that the rest of the materials in the full list remain equally valuable and relevant. All 106 resources were reviewed and included for their contribution to different aspects of media and climate literacy.

Image 1: The External Material subpage.

Modules

Among the highlighted materials are learning units from EDMO, UNESCO, and MIT; practical guides such as *The Debunking Handbook* and *The Climate Dictionary*; relevant reports published by organisations like the European Commission, OECD, NATO, and Climate Outreach; engaging podcasts that explore climate disinformation and adaptation; and digital tools such as the CLIMAAX CRA Toolbox and Bellingcat’s Open-Source Investigation Toolkit. This featured selection is intended to offer website visitors quick access to high-quality, thematically relevant materials, while the full collection remains available through the main Resources section.

While this collection is the first full set of materials, it is not meant to be final. The project team might add or adjust some of the resources later on, especially if there are new developments, suggestions or feedback from users. What is already included offers a solid starting point for supporting media literacy, particularly when it comes to dealing with disinformation and helping people become more resilient to climate-related narratives and manipulation.

3.2 Produced material

As part of Task 5.3, a wide range of educational and awareness-raising resources were developed to strengthen citizen resilience against climate change disinformation. These materials aim to build essential skills in media and digital literacy, critical thinking, and responsible online engagement, skills that are increasingly important in a time where misleading climate narratives can influence public attitudes and delay meaningful climate action. The resources were carefully designed to be accessible to a broad audience, including individual learners, educators, civil society actors, and local communities.

The materials produced include:

- **Educational modules** covering a wide range of topics aimed at strengthening skills in media literacy, understanding the nature and forms of climate change disinformation and applying practical ways to identify, fact-check and counter it.
- **Short articles** providing key points and concise explanations to raise awareness about climate change disinformation and the necessity of promoting media literacy.
- **Infographics** presenting visual concepts, trips and tricks to help individuals and communities strengthen their skills.
- **Videos** delivering practical demonstrations and useful information to enhance their media literacy capabilities.

Together, these outputs offer multiple entry points for users to engage with the topic depending on their level of knowledge and preferred format. Whether through interactive learning, visual guides, or concise reading materials, the content is aimed at supporting users in identifying and responding to disinformation, particularly in the context of climate change. Most importantly, the resources have been designed with flexibility in mind, so that trainers and facilitators can adapt them to their own teaching contexts, and learners can access them either independently or as part of structured learning.

All materials are made available through the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation, and a number of them are also shared on the Agora Community Hub and the [Adaptation AGORA website](#), ensuring maximum reach and long-term accessibility. By integrating these resources across the project's digital tools and platforms, Task 5.3 contributes not only to the project's immediate educational goals but also to its broader mission of supporting adaptation and resilience through informed, media-literate societies.

3.2.1 Modules

As climate change continues to dominate public discourse, so too does the spread of misleading or outright false information around it. The disinformation not only distorts public understanding but also risks delaying meaningful action. The Adaptation AGORA educational modules were designed with this challenge in mind to equip citizens with essential skills that help them navigate a complex information environment. At the same time, they work as helpful guides for educators, trainers, and others working with different groups. The modules are flexible: they can be delivered in full as standalone sessions or used selectively, with trainers free to extract specific parts that meet their audience’s needs.

Whether used in schools, community workshops or other places, they’re meant to support media literacy, especially in the context of climate change disinformation. The modules are organised under two main sections of the Academy website: one focused on [Media Literacy](#) and the other on [Climate Disinformation](#), making it easier for users to find the material that best suits their learning goals.

Image 2: The modules are organised under two main sections of the Academy website.

Each module is built around a clear set of objectives aimed at developing practical, real-world skills. They are meant to guide learners, not just theoretically, but with hands-on tools and approaches. In addition, each module includes a set of quizzes designed to help users test their understanding and reflect on what they have learned. These interactive elements support self-assessment and encourage users to engage more actively with the material.

The [Introduction to Media Literacy](#) module helps learners understand what media literacy is and why it matters today, both in traditional media like TV or newspapers, and in digital spaces like social media. It encourages participants to think about the messages they see and hear, spot possible bias, and see how different types of media can shape how we think and act. Learners are also guided to look at where information comes from, how stories are told, and how media can affect public life, especially on important topics like climate change and democracy. This module is a good starting point for anyone who hasn't studied media before.

Image 3: The Introduction to Media Literacy module.

In the [Digital Literacy](#) module, learners build on the basics and improve their skills in using and understanding digital content. They learn how to recognise different types of digital media, how filter bubbles and echo chambers work, and how to spot things such as fake accounts or disinformation online. The module also covers responsible online behaviour, including ethical sharing, understanding copyright, and protecting personal data. Educators can use this module to help learners become more aware of online risks and build safer, smarter digital habits.

Image 4: the Digital Literacy module.

The [Critical Thinking / Fallacies](#) module introduces basic critical thinking skills and shows how to spot common fallacies often used in climate change debates. It helps learners understand how to think critically and recognise misleading arguments, especially in the context of climate change. It introduces common types of fallacies—such as hasty generalisations or false dilemmas—and explains how they are used to spread misinformation. The course is based on the FLICC model (Fake Experts, Logical Fallacies, Impossible Expectations, Cherry Picking, Conspiracy Theories), which outlines five common techniques of science denial. Real-life examples, drawn from climate change discussions, are used throughout to help participants practise spotting these fallacies and build their resistance to disinformation.

Image 5: The Critical Thinking / Fallacies module.

The [Evaluating Information Sources](#) module deepens learners’ understanding of how to judge credibility. It introduces specific methods such as the 5Ws, the CARS checklist, and the CRAAP test

to help identify whether information is reliable. Learners are guided in distinguishing between types of sources—primary, secondary, and tertiary—and in using tools like reverse image search and fact-checking platforms. This practical skillset is vital for individuals who want to improve their ability to evaluate climate-related claims they encounter daily. The module also serves as a helpful guide for trainers teaching verification without overcomplicating the topic.

Image 6: The Evaluating Information Sources module.

In the [Fact-Checking and Verification](#) module, learners explore how to check whether something they read or see online is true. They learn basic techniques, such as using keywords and search operators, to find reliable information and are encouraged to look at different sources before making up their minds. One of the main goals is to build a clear and practical way of thinking when evaluating online claims. This helps learners feel more confident when they need to question false or misleading content. The module is a practical guide for anyone who wants to better understand how fact-checking works.

Image 7: The Fact-Checking and Verification module.

The [Engaging in Online Discussions / Online Safety](#) module looks at how people can take part in digital conversations about climate change in a constructive and respectful way. Learners are introduced to ten evidence-based principles for engaging in dialogue, which help them communicate more effectively and avoid falling into conflict or misinformation traps. The module also covers how to handle online harassment, protect one’s digital identity, and decide when to disengage from unproductive exchanges. For trainers, this module offers a clear and structured guide to supporting civil discourse and helping learners feel more comfortable in public digital spaces.

Image 8: The Engaging in Online Discussions / Online Safety module.

Finally, the [Psychology of Belief and Disinformation](#) module provides learners with an understanding of how beliefs are formed and why disinformation—especially about climate—can be so persuasive. This module guides learners through emotional, social, and cognitive mechanisms that affect judgment and highlights techniques such as “prebunking” and value-based framing.

These insights are particularly valuable for those wishing to build resilience at the community level, enabling participants not only to think critically for themselves but to support others in doing the same. Educators can rely on this module as a guide to explore the deeper psychological drivers behind susceptibility to disinformation.

Image 9: The Psychology of Belief and Disinformation module.

Moving on to the modules under the Climate Disinformation page, the [Understanding Climate Change](#) module offers a clear introduction to the basics of climate science and what adaptation involves. It helps learners become familiar with key concepts, such as the difference between climate and weather, and how climate change is observed and measured. It also explores some of the main impacts of climate change and the risks they present. In addition to the scientific side, the module highlights how climate change affects people in different ways, depending on their location and access to resources, and why fairness and inclusion are essential in any response. It provides a useful starting point for anyone interested in understanding why climate change matters and how we can respond with knowledge and responsibility.

Image 10: The Understanding Climate Change module.

The [Climate Change Communication](#) module introduces participants to key ideas and strategies behind communicating climate change effectively. It doesn't just stick to one way of explaining things. Instead, it walks learners through different communication models and styles, so they can better understand how to speak with different audiences. People attending the module will gain a clearer understanding of how messages about climate action can be shaped, misunderstood or even misused, and how to avoid that. It is helpful for educators, communicators and advocates who want to get their message across clearly and responsibly.

Image 11: The Climate Change Communication module.

In the [Climate Change Disinformation Tactics](#) module, participants are introduced to some of the main tactics used in spreading climate disinformation, from distortion to manipulation, and the broader patterns of misinformation campaigns. The goal here is to help learners become more aware of how false or misleading narratives are structured, so they can learn to recognise them in

real-world situations. The module also assists participants in developing a sharper sense of media awareness, which is particularly important for those involved in communication, education or advocacy work.

Image 12: The Climate Change Disinformation Tactics module.

The [Climate Change Disinformation Narratives](#) module explores the recurring narratives that are often seen in climate disinformation. It sheds light on the types of stories or arguments that are used to distract, delay or deny climate action. By understanding how these narratives are built and why they can be convincing, learners will strengthen their analytical thinking and create a sort of mental “toolkit” to challenge misleading messages more effectively. The module also touches on the role of values, identity, and ideology in shaping how people react to these kinds of narratives.

Image 13: The Climate Change Disinformation Narratives module.

The [Disinformation Campaigns - Case Studies](#) module provides an in-depth look at real case studies of how disinformation campaigns are organised and spread in the climate change context. It doesn't

just explain what happened, it tries to show why it worked and what lessons can be learned from it. Participants will be encouraged to critically reflect on the actors involved, their strategies, and the weaknesses in public communication systems that enable such campaigns to take root. It is a hands-on module and gives a more grounded view of the problem.

Image 14: The Disinformation Campaigns - Case Studies module.

As mentioned, the modules are designed to act not only as compact lessons but also as practical guides that trainers and educators can integrate into their own workshops, courses, or community sessions. Whether used in full or in part, they are flexible tools that help reinforce essential media, digital, and critical thinking skills. By enabling participants to assess content more thoughtfully, communicate more responsibly, and debunk misleading narratives more effectively, these modules make a substantial contribution towards a more informed and climate-resilient society.

3.2.2 Articles

A series of articles has been developed as part of the capacity-building resources of the Adaptation AGORA project. These articles complement the modules created for the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation and are intended to present selected topics in a more accessible format. Although they do not provide a deep or comprehensive understanding of each subject, they include several key points and examples to stimulate users' interest in further exploring the issues through additional reading, training, or educational activities.

The articles pursue two primary objectives on one hand, to introduce core ideas in a clear and engaging way, and on the other, to highlight the importance of education in addressing climate adaptation and climate action. By drawing from the content and structure of the Academy modules, they help readers recognise the value of building skills such as critical thinking, digital awareness, and source evaluation in the fight against disinformation. The articles are also useful for trainers

and educators, who may use them as short guides to encourage discussion, introduce a session, or underline the relevance of a specific topic.

Image 15: The blog section of the DA website.

Each piece draws attention to real-world challenges in the climate information landscape and connects them with the wider goal of supporting informed participation in climate action. The following 12 articles have been developed:

- [“Scrolling through the noise toward climate action”](#) addresses the growing influence of digital platforms and artificial intelligence on information exposure. It explores how digital literacy becomes essential for navigating algorithms and resisting climate-related disinformation online.
- [“Fighting climate disinformation starts with fact-checking”](#) introduces fact-checking as a practical skill and explains how simple tools and methods can help individuals assess the credibility of climate-related claims.
- [“Why media literacy matters in a changing climate”](#) focuses on how media narratives shape public understanding and policy views. It underlines the importance of developing critical perspectives toward media content when it comes to complex global issues.
- [“How do you know it’s true? Spotting reliable climate information online”](#) looks at how to evaluate sources and check for credibility online, offering straightforward techniques based on the module on evaluating information.

- [“Climate action undermined: The power of disinformation narratives”](#) examines the role of strategic narratives in weakening support for climate action. It highlights how disinformation can frame climate efforts as elitist or harmful, creating resistance among communities.
- [“How disinformation shapes the climate conversation”](#) reflects on organised campaigns and the ways emotional or misleading messaging is used to influence opinion and delay climate policies.
- [“Why people believe climate disinformation and how we can respond”](#) draws from the psychology of belief to explain how emotions, cognitive biases, and social dynamics contribute to the spread of disinformation, and what can be done to counter this.
- [“Joining the climate conversation: Why how you talk online matters”](#) looks at the importance of respectful and constructive online communication, especially when engaging in climate discussions on social platforms.
- [“Communicating climate change: Words matter more than ever”](#) builds on the communication module and explains how strategic framing, inclusiveness, and clarity are key to effectively raising awareness and promoting climate action.
- [“Critical thinking and fallacies: Essential tools against climate misinformation”](#) explores how flawed reasoning, including logical fallacies, can weaken public understanding. It introduces tools like the FLICC framework and focuses on fallacy literacy as a way to build resistance against manipulative arguments.
- [“How climate change misinformation spreads: Tactics and technics”](#) presents a clear overview of how disinformation moves through different platforms, identifying its sources and the motivations behind its creation and amplification.
- [“Before We Act, We Learn: The Fundamentals of Climate Change”](#) presents the basic information on climate change in a comprehensive and simple way.

While these articles are not meant to replace the structured learning experience of the Academy, they play a valuable role in creating an informative and motivating environment that encourages users to reflect, seek more knowledge, and understand the role of education in strengthening resilience to climate-related disinformation.

All articles will be made available through the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation, where they will form part of the wider set of capacity-building resources accessible to users. In addition, a dedicated section will be created on the Adaptation AGORA project website, allowing visitors to find and browse the full set of articles easily. They will also be published on the Adaptation Hub, which is hosted on the weADAPT platform. The Hub will remain live after the completion of the project, supporting the preservation and visibility of project outcomes. Publishing the articles across all three platforms will contribute to the project’s legacy and ensure that these

resources continue to be used and shared by educators, civil society groups, and individuals interested in strengthening their understanding and resilience to climate-related disinformation.

3.2.3 Graphics

A total of eight visual graphics were developed to support the communication goals of the project and help make key concepts around media literacy and climate change disinformation more accessible. These visuals are meant to complement the educational content provided through the project's digital tools and raise awareness in a more engaging and direct way. The graphics are available online on the [Graphics and Videos](#) subpage, which can be found on the Media Literacy page of the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation. Users can visit the section to view the visuals and download them freely for use in their own awareness-raising activities, workshops, or presentations.

One of the graphics created presents the *five main techniques of science denial*, based on the work of John Cook: fake experts, logical fallacies, impossible expectations, cherry-picking, and conspiracy theories. The aim is to help users recognise common patterns used to undermine scientific facts and generate confusion.

Image 16: Graphic - The five techniques of science denial by John Cook.

Another graphic explores the concept of *filter bubbles and echo chambers*, explaining how personalised algorithms and user preferences can shape what kind of information people see online. It highlights how this limited exposure to diverse viewpoints can reinforce existing beliefs and make individuals more susceptible to disinformation. The aim is to raise awareness about the digital environment in which most people consume information and how this affects their perception of climate issues.

Image 17: Graphic - Filter bubbles and echo chambers.

Filter bubbles & echo chambers

Social media platforms use algorithms to shape what you see — based on what you click, like, and share.

Over time, this creates filter bubbles, where you mostly see content that confirms your existing views. A related idea is echo chambers—online spaces where similar opinions are repeated and rarely challenged. These digital traps can:

- Make it seem like everyone agrees with you (even if they don't)
- Increase polarisation and harm respectful debate
- Limit critical thinking on complex topics
- Help spread climate change disinformation by hiding credible sources and repeating false claims

To break out, start by following different sources, listening to a range of voices, and staying curious about other viewpoints.

Learn more in our course at the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation.

adaptation Agora
agoraclimatedisinfo.eu

One of the graphics introduces the basics of *Boolean search techniques*, offering practical tips for improving online searches. It explains how using simple operators like AND, OR, and NOT can help users refine their search results and access more relevant and trustworthy information. This visual is particularly useful for those who want to become more effective in navigating online content, whether they are verifying a claim or simply looking for credible sources on climate-related topics.

Image 18: Graphic - Boolean search techniques.

Boolean Search
A Boolean search allows you to use words or symbols to limit, expand, or specify your search criteria.

Boolean operators		Example
Search for contents that includes two or more words	AND	Climate AND weather AND change
Search for content that includes one or another words	OR	Disinformation OR misinformation
Exclude a word or more from your search	-	Climate -change
Search for specific words within a certain word count in a sentence.	AROUND (n)	Climate AROUND (5) disinformation
Search for an exact phrase	" "	"climate change"
Search for a specific word or phrase in the title	intitle	intitle:Climate
Search for a specific word or phrase in the text	intext	intext:Climate
Find synonyms of a term	~	~ academic
Search for results in a specific site	site:	site:nasa.gov
Search for a specific word or phrase in the source	source:	source:education

Using Boolean Search

Example with Boolean search
"climate change" site:nasa.gov
Shows only results from NASA's official website.

Quotation marks but no site filter
"climate change" nasa
Keeps the phrase together but still includes results from various sources.

Broad search without filters
climate change NASA
Returns many results from different websites -- not just NASA.

You can then see differences in search results using or not using Boolean search!

Learn more at agoraclimateadvisory.eu

The *digital literate person* graphic defines the characteristics of a digitally literate individual. It outlines key behaviours such as questioning the origin of content, assessing credibility and bias, and understanding the role of algorithms in shaping online experiences. The graphic serves as a prompt for self-reflection and learning, motivating users to develop these essential skills.

Image 19: Graphic – Digital Literate Person.

The *fake accounts* graphic highlights the role of fake accounts—bots or impersonators—in spreading disinformation. It explains how these accounts mimic credible sources, coordinate narratives, and create artificial waves of support or outrage. By raising awareness of such tactics, the visual promotes digital literacy as a vital defence against manipulation. It invites users to explore tools and strategies to detect and counter disinformation, reinforcing the importance of being informed and critical in digital spaces.

Image 20: Graphic - Fake Accounts.

The “What is an argument? A quick guide to logic and reasoning” graphic breaks down the structure of a logical argument, making it easier to understand how reasoning works. It defines what an argument is, outlines its core components—premises, conclusion, and inference—and explains how

faulty logic can lead to fallacies. This visual is a concise introduction to critical thinking and logical evaluation, ideal for anyone looking to sharpen their reasoning skills.

Image 21: Graphic - What is an argument? A quick guide to logic and reasoning.

The “Think before you share – Media literacy tips for navigating climate information” infographic offers practical questions to consider before sharing climate-related content online. It encourages users to assess the source, purpose, emotional tone, and completeness of information, and to verify claims using credible tools. The aim is to build habits of thoughtful consumption and sharing of content, especially during the climate crisis, where misleading information is widespread. The graphic underscores how critical thinking contributes to greater climate resilience.

Image 22: Graphic - Think before you share – Media literacy tips for navigating climate information.

Think Before You Share
Media Literacy Tips for Navigating Climate Information

In the age of climate crisis, not all information is created equal. Before you trust or repost something, ask yourself:

- Who created this message?**
A journalist? Scientist? Activist? Government source? Or just an anonymous account?
- What is their purpose?**
Are they trying to inform, persuade, spark outrage, or push an agenda?
- Is it based on facts or just emotion?**
Look for credible data, expert sources, and scientific consensus. Beware of emotional manipulation.
- Are certain voices being amplified or silenced?**
Whose perspective is missing? Are frontline communities, scientists, or youth activists heard?
- What's missing or left unsaid?**
Is the story missing: Historical context? Impact on vulnerable groups? Possible solutions?
- How can I verify this?**
Use tools like: Fact-checking websites, Reverse image search, Trusted sources (IPCC, NASA, credible news outlets)

Critical Thinking = Climate Resilience

Climate change is complex – often politicised, sometimes even manipulated. Some messages simplify, distort, or twist reality to fit a narrative.

Stay informed. Stay curious.
Learn how in our course at the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation.
Visit <https://agoraclimatedisinfo.eu/>

Lastly, a visual on *cross-checking information* illustrates how different sources can present the same event in very different ways. It encourages users to compare multiple sources before forming an opinion, reinforcing the importance of critical thinking and information verification in the face of climate-related disinformation.

**Climate Change in the Headlines:
Why Cross-Checking Sources Matters**

- A TV news report claims a recent climate protest turned violent.
- A newspaper article describes it as peaceful but urgent.
- Social media posts show both calm speeches and tense police encounters.

If you accept only one version, your view may be biased. But by comparing multiple sources – news, eyewitness accounts, and videos – you get a clearer, more accurate picture.

Cross-check to stay informed.
Learn how in our Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation course.
Visit <https://agoraclimatedisinfo.eu/>

These visuals will be used across the project’s communication channels. The idea is to simplify complex ideas and encourage people to reflect on how they process and share information, especially in relation to climate change. They are not meant to replace the course content but to introduce and reinforce key messages in a visually appealing and easy-to-digest format.

3.2.4 Videos

Three short videos were created to support the development of the capacity-building skills in an engaging way. The main idea behind them is to promote necessary skills that are useful not only in the digital space but also in everyday life. These videos will be shared through the digital tools developed as part of the project. The idea is to make these skills more visible and easier to grasp by offering short, focused material that encourages active engagement with the project’s resources.

The first [video](#) is meant to help users navigate the Digital Academy. It provides a short introduction to the platform and gives an overview of the available materials that aim to build media literacy skills and help users better understand and respond to climate-related disinformation. It is designed to be practical and easy to follow, offering a clear starting point for anyone visiting the platform for the first time.

Image 23: Screenshot from the video “Introducing the Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation”.

The second and third videos focus more on the topics of content creation and content evaluation. These were selected because they are considered essential in the broader field of media literacy and directly connected to promoting climate adaptation and responsible public communication. In an era where online content plays an essential role in shaping opinions and behaviours, it is important that people understand how to evaluate and share information.

In the video dedicated to [content creation](#), we highlight simple but important principles to support responsible online behaviour. These include checking the accuracy of information, distinguishing between personal opinions and facts, being respectful in language and tone, protecting the privacy of others, and thinking carefully about why something is being posted and who it might affect. These basic guidelines aim to encourage users to pause and reflect before publishing content online.

Image 24: Screenshot from the video “Principles for ethical content creation”.

We also introduce the well-known ["5Ws" method](#)—who, what, when, where, and why—as a useful way to assess whether information found online is reliable. The video invites users to ask questions such as: Who created the content? Are they a credible source? What is being said and is it backed by facts? When was it published and is it still relevant? Where is it hosted and does the platform seem trustworthy? And finally, why was it created, what purpose does it serve, and who benefits from it?

Image 25: Screenshot from the video “The 5 Ws”.

We tried to keep the content simple, relatable, and easy to understand. The purpose of these videos is not only to raise awareness but also to offer viewers concrete steps they can take to become more thoughtful and better informed when interacting online. These videos complement the broader set of capacity building skills developed in the framework of the project, which aim to strengthen media literacy, improve critical thinking, and help users become more resilient to climate change disinformation.

4. Synergies between Task 5.3 and other tasks

The work carried out under Task 5.3, which focused on strengthening citizen resilience against climate change disinformation, is closely interlinked with several other outcomes within the project. The capacity building materials produced as part of this task — including short videos, articles, modules and graphics — are not confined to a single platform or output. Instead, they have been integrated across various tasks, ensuring broader impact, sustainability, and effective dissemination.

Task 5.3 is intrinsically connected with Task 3.5 (Digital Academy against Climate Change Disinformation), where all the materials developed under 5.3 have been made available. This direct

integration guarantees that citizens have structured, user-friendly access to the educational content and reinforces the consistency and quality of the learning experience.

One of the most direct connections is with the Agora Community Hub (Task 3.3), which serves as a meeting point to empower local communities to share needs, knowledge and experiences on climate adaptation issues and solutions. Resources from Task 5.3, such as the blog posts, contribute directly to this effort by enhancing users' media literacy skills and their ability to detect and respond to climate-related disinformation. In this way, the materials support not only disinformation resilience but also wider climate resilience. The Hub is built as a weADAPT microsite, and the inclusion of the educational content will help ensure that the knowledge and tools developed throughout the project will remain accessible and useful also after the end of the project, contributing to the long-term legacy of the initiative.

Moreover, Task 2.2, which focuses on the development of a gamified mobile app, has also benefited from the outcomes of Task 5.3. Specifically, two thematic categories were created in the app: *climate disinformation* and *media literacy*, each comprising approximately 200 questions. These questions were developed based on the content produced under Task 5.3. There is a strong link between the Academy and the app: users who complete the lessons provided through the Academy can test their knowledge further by accessing the app, which offers a broader set of questions and allows for interactive engagement.

Image 26: The categories of the AGORA quiz.

Lastly, Task 5.3 has also been informed by Task 5.1, which aimed to co-design and deploy citizen science initiatives in the areas of climate change adaptation and tackling disinformation. The insights from Task 5.1 helped inform the structure and relevance of the content produced in 5.3, ensuring that the material aligns with the actual needs and experiences of citizens.

Overall, the synergies between Task 5.3 and other work packages highlight the importance of cross-cutting collaboration when it comes to building resilience to climate disinformation. Making reliable, accessible information widely available across platforms is essential for strengthening media literacy, enabling effective adaptation, and supporting long-term climate resilience.

5. Conclusion

The work undertaken in Task 5.3 of the Adaptation AGORA project has helped lay the groundwork for a more informed and resilient public when it comes to climate change disinformation. By selecting, creating, and sharing a wide range of educational materials — from interactive modules and videos to articles, infographics, and external resources — the project has made important tools available to citizens, educators, and civil society actors across Europe.

One of the key strengths of this task has been its practical focus. Instead of merely outlining the challenges posed by disinformation, the materials developed aim to provide people with real, everyday skills to recognise false or misleading information, understand how media messages are shaped, and engage with others constructively, whether online or in person. Their flexible design allows them to be used in different settings, including school. They have already been put into practice through the Pilots organised within the project, as well as by some followers, who have successfully integrated them into their activities, demonstrating their adaptability and real-world impact, in community spaces, and online training environments.

Additionally, the strong collaboration with other outputs of the project has helped ensure the materials developed in Task 5.3 are contextually integrated within the broader framework. They are embedded in the broader Adaptation AGORA ecosystem, which increases their reach and long-term impact. In particular, Task 5.3 has contributed to a range of other activities, including WP2's Pilots, discussions on citizen engagement, several thematic workshops, and the work in WP4 on the role of climate change disinformation in policy design. These synergies between tasks have allowed for consistent messaging and a more seamless user experience.

While it was not the aim of this project to have these materials in diverse local languages, some of them will be translated into selected languages through task 5.4. This will help ensure that more citizens from different backgrounds — including those who may not have had the opportunity to learn English — can access, understand, and benefit from the resources, broadening their reach and impact.

The importance of media literacy capacity building resources was also reinforced during the 2025 Global Symposium on Climate Justice and Impacted Populations - (July 28-31), where practitioners, policy makers, and academicians from Africa, Europe, Asia, and Latin America discussed shared challenges in climate adaptation. Among the pressing issues identified was the lack of adequate data, limited public awareness, and the circulation of false or misleading information across different groups of individuals. Furthermore, some experts commented on the need to involve ancestral knowledge from communities that have been in touch with certain geographical areas, and this too should be considered as valuable information. This reinforces the importance of elements such as capacity building, tackling climate change disinformation to ensure that climate

change adaptation can be effectively addressed and citizens can be meaningfully involved. The Adaptation AGORA project was able to shed light on this matter during the conference, adding on alternative tools and elements such as the disinformation academy with all the various materials developed under task 5.3.

In the end, resilience against climate disinformation is not only about identifying what is false, but also about strengthening what is true, building trust in communities, and empowering people to take part in climate solutions. Task 5.3 has contributed to this wider goal by giving citizens the tools to think more critically, communicate more responsibly, and act with confidence in the face of misinformation.

References

- Berinsky, A. J. (2017). Rumors and Health Care Reform: Experiments in Political Misinformation. *British Journal of Political Science*, 47(2), 241–262. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007123415000186>
- Cook J, Lewandowsky S, Ecker UKH (2017) Neutralizing misinformation through inoculation: Exposing misleading argumentation techniques reduces their influence. *PLoS ONE* 12(5): e0175799. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0175799>
- Daume, S. (2024). Online misinformation during extreme weather emergencies: Short-term information hazard or long-term influence on climate change perceptions? *Environmental Research Communications*, 6(2), 022001. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ad1b67>
- Directorate-General for Climate Action. (2022). *How to talk to people about climate action: Toolkit*. European Climate Pact. [https://climate-pact.europa.eu/get-inspired/how-talk-people-about-climate-action_en`](https://climate-pact.europa.eu/get-inspired/how-talk-people-about-climate-action_en)
- Cook, J., Lewandowsky, S., & Ecker, U. K. H. (2017). Neutralizing misinformation through inoculation: Exposing misleading argumentation techniques reduces their influence. *PLOS ONE*, 12(5), e0175799. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0175799>
- European Commission. (2007). *A European approach to media literacy in the digital environment* (Communication No. COM (2007) 833 final). Eur-Lex. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52007DC0833&from=el>
- European Commission. (2024). *Tackling climate-related disinformation*. Retrieved from https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-disinformation_en
- European Commission. (2025). *Tackling online disinformation*. Shaping Europe’s digital future. Retrieved from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/online-disinformation>
- European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2022). *Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act)* (OJ L 277, pp. 1–102). EUR-Lex. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/2065/oj>
- Ecker, U.K.H., Lewandowsky, S., Cook, J. *et al.* The psychological drivers of misinformation belief and its resistance to correction. *Nat Rev Psychol* 1, 13–29 (2022). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44159-021-00006-y>

Flore, M., Balahur, A., Podavini, A., & Verile, M. (2019). *Understanding citizens' vulnerabilities to disinformation and data-driven propaganda: Case study—the 2018 Italian general election* (EUR 29741 EN). Publications Office of the European Union. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2760/919835>

Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy. (2024). *Addressing rampant climate disinformation*. Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy. Retrieved from <https://www.globalcovenantofmayors.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Addressing-Rampant-Climate-Disinformation-FINAL-.pdf>

IPCC. (2018). *Global warming of 1.5°C: Summary for policymakers*. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Retrieved from <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>

Kahan, D. M. (2013). Ideology, motivated reasoning, and cognitive reflection. *Judgment and Decision Making*, 8(4), 407–424. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1930297500005271>

Lewandowsky, S., Cook, J., Ecker, U. K. H., et. all. (2020). *The debunking handbook 2020*. Retrieved from <https://sks.to/db2020>

Milli, S., Carroll, M., Wang, Y., Pandey, S., Zhao, S., & Dragan, A. D. (2025, March 5). Engagement, user satisfaction, and the amplification of divisive content on social media. *PNAS Nexus*, 4(3), Article pgaf062. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgaf062>

Nusche, D., M. Fuster Rabella and S. Lauterbach (2024), “Rethinking education in the context of climate change: Leverage points for transformative change”, *OECD Education Working Papers*, No. 307, OECD Publishing, Paris. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1787/f14c8a81-en>.

van der Linden, S., Roozenbeek, J., & Compton, J. (2020). Inoculating against fake news about COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 566790. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.566790>

Appendix

List of resources collected

	Title	Author / Publisher	Link
1	Guía para periodistas sobre cambio climático y biodiversidad	Banco Interamericano de Desarrollo (BID)	https://publications.iadb.org/es/guia-para-periodistas-sobre-cambio-climatico-y-biodiversidad
2	Desfake Clima	Verificat + CREAM	https://www.cream.cat/es/investigacion/directorio-de-investigaciondesfake-clima
3	Deciphering Climate Disinformation	EcoMedia Literacy	https://ecomedia-literacy.org/deciphering-climate-disinformation/
4	Climate Curricular Materials	MIT Climate Action Through Education	https://medialiteracynow.org/document/climate-literacy-unit/
5	Checkology	News Literacy Project	https://get.checkology.org/explore/
6	El Mural del Clima	La Fresque du Climat	https://restore.fresqueduclimat.org/memo/en-US/game/grid
7	Bomba Viral, board game	Muy Waso Foundation	https://muywaso.com/presentaremos-nuestro-primer-juego-de-mesa-en-alemania/
8	Voces Jóvenes por el Cambio Climático	Glocalminds / múltiples ONGs	https://www.youtube.com/@youngvoicesforplanet
9	Met Office - Toolkit contra la desinformación	Met Office UK	https://weather.metoffice.gov.uk/climate-change/tackling-climate-misinformation
10	True or false? How to defend yourself against disinformation	European Commission	https://commission.europa.eu/news/true-or-false-how-defend-yourself-against-disinformation-2024-10-23_es
11	Promoting Reliable Knowledge about Climate Change: A Systematic Review of Effective Measures to Resist	Aliaksandr Herasimenka, Xianlingchen Wang, Ralph Schroeder	https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.23814

	Manipulation on Social Media		
12	Cómo detectar desinformación y sesgos climáticos	Sentient Media	https://sentientmedia.org/es/como-detectar-la-desinformacion-y-los-sesgos-sobre-el-clima-y-la-alimentacion-en-las-noticias/
13	The Misinformation Game	University of Western Australia & Ecker Memory & Cognition Lab	https://misinfogame.com/
14	Climate Outreach: Reports & guides	Climate Outreach	https://climateoutreach.org/reports/
15	Media and Information Literacy e-platform - Infographics	UNESCO	https://www.unesco.org/mil4teachers/en/infographics
16	MediaWise	Poynter Institute	https://www.poynter.org/mediawise/
17	Critical Thinking about Climate - a video series by John Cook	Skeptical Science	https://skepticalscience.com/news.php?n=4877
18	Russia 'Spread Conspiracy Theories and Attacked Climate Scientists in Poland'	Joey Grostern / DeSmog	https://www.desmog.com/2025/02/03/russia-spread-conspiracy-theories-and-attacked-climate-scientists-in-poland/
19	Climate Change Deniers vs The Consensus	Information is Beautiful	https://informationisbeautiful.net/visualizations/climate-change-deniers-vs-the-consensus/
20	Climate Misinformation Playbook	Union of Concerned Scientists	https://ucsusa.org/resources/disinformation-playbook
21	The Debunking Handbook 2020	John Cook et al.	https://www.climatechangecommunication.org/debunking-handbook-2020/
22	Everyday Climate Champions	Everyday Climate Champions	https://open.spotify.com/show/2vRZ4S9f7mxWKH3IWksX0X

23	Global roadmap for information as a public good in the face of the environmental crisis: key takeaways and a strategy to implement the 2024 World Press Freedom Day Call for Action	UNESCO	https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000391126
24	How to cover climate change news without promoting misinformation?	Chequeado (Fermín Koop y Nira Dinerstein)	https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/ceneam/recursos/pag-web/como-cubrir-noticias-cc-sin-desinformacion.html
25	Reporting extreme weather and climate change: A guide for journalists	Ben Clarke (University of Oxford) Friederike Otto (Imperial College London)	https://www.worldweatherattribution.org/wp-content/uploads/ENG_WWA-Reporting-extreme-weather-and-climate-change.pdf
26	Peritia Toolkit	PERITIA Project	https://peritia-trust.eu/toolkit/
27	PERITIA Lectures [Un]Truths: Trust in an Age of Disinformation	PERITIA Project	https://peritia-trust.eu/peritia-lectures/
28	SLACC Climate lies	SLACC Project	https://slacc-project.eu/climate-lies/
29	SLACC Fact checking sites	SLACC Project	https://slacc-project.eu/media/annex-1-fact-checking-sites.pdf
30	TINTIN online platform and curriculum	TINTIN Project	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1OsJyTJuxCKwGqTZ-r7K075jeru1My9Zc/view
31	TINTIN Handbook for Climate Change Education	TINTIN Project	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bJQfx2E70H8xyUfcTQEGKeb-zTPo8Vqy/view
32	Anti-Rumour Guidebook: Fake news, conspiracy theories and hot to spot them	Anti-Rumour Project	https://anti-rumour.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/PR1.A5-Creation-of-the-Guidebook_Final-Version2.pdf
33	Anti-Rumour ToolKit	Anti-Rumour Project	https://view.genial.ly/653fab0ddd9e6500112af907

34	Journey through the MILtiverse: media and information literacy toolkit for youth organizations	UNESCO	https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000392035
35	Climate Visuals: Seven principles for visual climate change communication	Climate Outreach	https://climateoutreach.org/reports/climate-visuals-seven-principles-for-visual-climate-change-communication/
36	Breaking Down Climate Misinformation with Amy Westervelt and John Cook	Climate One	https://www.climateone.org/audio/breaking-down-climate-misinformation-amy-westervelt-and-john-cook
37	Climate change conspiracy memes on Instagram extend across the web	First Draft	https://firstdraftnews.org/articles/climate-change-misinformation-conspiracy-memes/
38	Articles on Psychology of climate change denial	The Conversation	https://theconversation.com/topics/psychology-of-climate-change-denial-77174
39	Artists, Information Literacy & Climate Change	OER Commons	https://oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/79471/overview
40	Climate Change Disinformation and How to Combat It	Stephan Lewandowsky / Annual Reviews	https://www.annualreviews.org/content/journals/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-090419-102409
41	Addressing Rampant Climate Disinformation	Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy	https://www.globalcovenantofmayors.org/press/addressing-rampant-climate-disinformation/
42	What are climate misinformation and disinformation and what is their impact?	London School of Economics and Political Science	https://www.lse.ac.uk/granthaminstitute/explainers/what-are-climate-misinformation-and-disinformation/
43	What are climate misinformation and disinformation and how can we tackle them?	UNDP	https://climatepromise.undp.org/news-and-stories/what-are-climate-misinformation-and-disinformation-and-how-can-we-tackle-them

44	Climate Disinformation	European Commission	https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-disinformation_en
45	F-L-I-C-C: The most common disinformation tricks of science deniers	Klimafakten	https://www.klimafakten.de/kommunikation/f-l-i-c-c-most-common-disinformation-tricks-science-deniers
46	Infographic: Beyond Fake News – 10 Types of Misleading News – Seventeen Languages	EAVI	https://eavi.eu/beyond-fake-news-10-types-misleading-info/
47	Global Initiative for Information Integrity on Climate Change	UNESCO	https://www.unesco.org/en/information-integrity-climate-change
48	Climate Disinformation – EC Library Guide: Selected research articles	European Commission	https://ec.europa-eu.libguides.com/climate-disinformation/research/articles
49	Tactics of Disinformation	CISA	https://www.cisa.gov/sites/default/files/publications/tactics-of-disinformation_508.pdf
50	Steps and Tools for Evaluating the News	Rutgers University	https://libguides.rutgers.edu/fake_news
51	Countering Disinformation Effectively: An Evidence-Based Policy Guide	Carnegie	https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/01/countering-disinformation-effectively-an-evidence-based-policy-guide
52	Navigating Climate Misinformation	CAAD	https://caad.info/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Journalist-Field-Guide-3pager.pdf
53	The Basics of Climate Change	Copernicus	https://royalsociety.org/news-resources/projects/climate-change-evidence-causes/basics-of-climate-change/#:~:text=Arctic%20summer%20sea%20ice%20cover,and%20ice%20sheets%20on%20land
54	Shared socioeconomic pathways	Baste et al. 2021	https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Shared-socioeconomic-pathways-in-the-figure-OECD-stands-for-Organisation-for-Economic_fig2_349636920

55	What is climate data?	Ilse Boonstra, SEI Tallinn	https://agoradigitalacademy.dataclimate.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Graphical-abstract-938x1536.png
56	CLIMAAX CRA toolbox.	CLIMAAX	https://www.climaax.eu/handbook/toolbox/
57	Transformational adaptation: what it is, why it matters & what is needed	WeAdapt	https://weadapt.org/knowledge-base/governance-institutions-and-policy/transformational-adaptation/
58	Transformative Adaptation: Unlocking The Power of Local Governance IWMI	IWMI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p4Ag0KtxYsY
59	Towards ‘just resilience’: leaving no one behind when adapting to climate change	EEA	https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/just-resilience-leaving-no-one-behind
60	This is just how unfair climate change is	DW Planet A	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pHRu0VV-Dbw&ab_channel=DWPlanetA
61	Intersectionality and Climate Change	Yale	https://sustainability.yale.edu/explainers/yale-experts-explain-intersectionality-and-climate-change
62	Globally representative evidence on the actual and perceived support for climate action	Peter Andre, Teodora Boneva, Felix Chopra & Armin Falk	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41558-024-01925-3
63	Why Gender Matters for Effective Adaptation to Climate Change	NAP Global Network	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=luO8phhdfsA&ab_channel=NAPGlobalNetwork
64	DestinE Videos & Podcasts	Destination Earth Eu	https://destination-earth.eu/videos-podcasts/
65	Conoscere i cambiamenti climatici	ISPRA ambiente	https://climadat.isprambiente.it/conoscere-i-cambiamenti-climatici/

66	Infographic: how climate change is affecting Europe	European Parliament	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20180905STO11945/infographic-how-climate-change-is-affecting-europe
67	A Controversial Play — and What It Taught Me About the Psychology of Climate David Finnigan	TED	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MHZMQLDr-OA
68	A temperature check on climate communication: where are we?	Nature	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-025-04585-6
69	Impact, adaptation and vulnerability	IPCC	https://ca1-eci.edcdn.com/infographics/IPCC_WGII_Impacts_27_Feb_23.pdf?v=1677409825
70	Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation & Vulnerability - Full video	IPCC	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SDRxfuEvgGg
71	Climate Change Adaptation Digital Twin: a window to the future of our Planet	ECMFW	https://destine.ecmwf.int/news/climate-change-adaptation-digital-twin-a-window-to-the-future-of-our-planet/
72	Earthday platform	Earthday	https://www.earthday.org/actions/host-a-community-climate-discussion/
73	Psychological inoculation strategies to fight climate disinformation across 12 countries	Nature	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-023-01736-0
74	Why teach critical thinking about climate change?	NCSE	https://ncse.ngo/why-teach-critical-thinking-about-climate-change
75	These 3 climate misinformation campaigns are operating during the election run-up. Here's how to spot them	The conversation	https://theconversation.com/these-3-climate-misinformation-campaigns-are-operating-during-the-election-run-up-heres-how-to-spot-them-253441

76	Use 'more cheer, less fear' for effective climate communication	UNESCO	https://en.unesco.org/inclusivepolicylab/analytics/use-more-cheer-less-fear-effective-climate-communication
77	The Role of Emotional Engagement in Climate Messaging	Earth.org	https://earth.org/the-role-of-emotional-engagement-in-climate-messaging/
78	Empowering young people through climate literacy	OECD	https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2024/11/ClimateBrochure_Nov2024_FIN.pdf/_jcr_content/renditions/original./ClimateBrochure_Nov2024_FIN.pdf
79	Generative AI tools can enhance climate literacy but must be checked for biases and inaccuracies	Nature	https://www.nature.com/articles/s43247-024-01392-w
80	Communicating on climate change and health Toolkit for health professionals	World Health Organization	https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240090224
81	Digital disinformation strategies of European climate change obstructionist think tanks	Frontiers	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/communication/articles/10.3389/fcomm.2024.1470343/full
82	Disinformation as an obstructionist strategy in climate change mitigation: a review of the scientific literature for a systemic understanding of the phenomenon	European Commission	https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/4-169
83	Communication Toolkit on Gender and Climate	The Greens EFA	https://www.greens-efa.eu/files/assets/docs/gender_toolkit.pdf
84	Implications for biodiversity of Global Warming	WWF/IPCC	https://awsassets.panda.org/img/original/biodiversity_ipcc.gif

85	The Resilience Podcast: How the Media Covers Climate Adaptation	UN Environment Programme	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jLMv-p570mQ
86	Strengthening Climate Adaptation and Resilience	One UN Climate Change Learning Partnership	https://unccelearn.org/course/view.php?id=207&page=overview
87	EDMO Training Series on Climate Disinformation- Module 1: Understanding climate disinformation	EDMO	https://edmo.eu/training/edmo-training-series-on-climate-disinformation-module-1/
89	EDMO: Repository Of Fact-Checking Articles	EDMO	https://edmo.eu/resources/repositories/repository-of-fact-checking-articles/
90	Media Literacy Champions: Training program	Gloucestershire Healthy Living and Learning (GHLL)	https://www.ghll.org.uk/pshe-curriculum/media-literacy-champions-/
91	The Climate Dictionary: An everyday guide to climate change	United Nations Development Programme	https://climatepromise.undp.org/news-and-stories/climate-dictionary-everyday-guide-climate-change
92	Climate 101: An interactive dictionary about climate change	One UN Climate Change Learning Partnership	https://static.unccelearn.org/Net_Zero_101/Interactive/#/
93	Module 1: Introduction to Media & Information Literacy and Key Concepts	UNESCO	https://www.unesco.org/mil4teachers/en/module1
94	ERGA Media Literacy Report Recommendations for key principles, best practices and a Media Literacy	European Regulators Group for Audiovisual Media Services	https://erga-online.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/ERGA-AG3-2021-Report-on-Media-Literacy.pdf

	Toolbox for Video-sharing Platforms		
95	How and why does misinformation spread?	American Psychology Association	https://www.apa.org/topics/journalism-facts/how-why-misinformation-spreads
96	Speaking of Psychology: Stopping the spread of misinformation, with Sander van der Linden, PhD	American Psychology Association	https://www.apa.org/news/podcasts/speaking-of-psychology/stopping-spread-misinformation
97	AI Literacy, Explained	MIT Open Learning	https://openlearning.mit.edu/news/ai-literacy-explained
98	Evaluating Sources	Harvard Guide to Using Sources	https://usingsources.fas.harvard.edu/evaluating-sources-0
99	HEAT (Harmful Environmental Agendas & Tactics)	EU DisinfoLab & Logically	https://www.disinfo.eu/heat-harmful-environmental-agendas-and-tactics/
100	Climate Change & Security Impact Assessment - The NATO Secretary General's report	NATO	https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2024/7/pdf/240709-Climate-Security-Impact.pdf
101	Fertile Ground for Disinformation: From Spreading Climate Change Misinformation to Undermining Climate Action: How the Farmers' Protests Were Used to Influence Audiences	Science Feedback, Newtral, EFCSN, European Climate Foundation	https://euroclimatecheck.com/climate-facts-europe/#fertilegrounds
102	Climate Conspiracies in the Western Balkans: Widely Imported and Persistently Repeated	Metamorphosis, European Climate Foundation	https://euroclimatecheck.com/climate-facts-europe/#climateconspiracies

103	Climate Denialism in Italy, Spain, and Greece Stemming from Extreme Weather Events	Maldita, Facta, Ellinika Hoaxes, EFCSN	https://euroclimatecheck.com/climate-facts-europe/#climatedenialism
104	Capi the chatbot	Codesinfo – Innovation Fund for Combating Disinformation	https://capi.ambiental.media/
105	Bellingcat’s Online Open Source Investigation Toolkit	Bellingcat	https://bellingcat.gitbook.io/toolkit
106	European Environment Agency - Data Hub	European Environment Agency	https://shorturl.at/UyDsc

